

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA MILLATLARARO MUNOSABATLAR.

Meliqulov Bobur

SamDCHTI Gumanitar fanlar va axborot texnologiyalari kafedrası o'qituvchisi.

bmeliqulov92@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Maqolada globallashuv sharoitida O'zbekistonda millatlararo munosabatlarning rivojlanishi, uning ijtimoiy-siyosiy va madaniy jihatlari tahlil etilgan. Muallif O'zbekistonning ko'p millatli jamiyat sifatidagi xususiyatlarini, turli etnik guruhlar o'rtasidagi hamjihatlik va bag'rikenglik muhitini saqlash va rivojlantirish yo'lidagi davlat siyosatini yoritadi. Shuningdek, millatlararo munosabatlarga ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi global omillar, jumladan, migratsiya jarayonlari, axborot makonining kengayishi va xalqaro integratsiya masalalariga e'tibor qaratiladi. Maqolada O'zbekistonda milliy va diniy bag'rikenglikni mustahkamlashga qaratilgan huquqiy-me'yoriy asoslar, amaliy choralar va kelgusidagi istiqbollar haqida ham so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Globallashuv, O'zbekiston, millatlararo munosabatlar, bag'rikenglik, etnik guruhlar, ijtimoiy barqarorlik, madaniy xilma-xillik, integratsiya, milliy siyosat, migratsiya, xalqaro munosabatlar, diniy bag'rikenglik, huquqiy-me'yoriy asoslar, ijtimoiy hamjihatlik, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION.

Author: Melikulov Bobur
Teacher of the Department of
Humanities and Information
Technologies of SamDCHTI.

Annotation: The article analyzes the development of interethnic relations in Uzbekistan in the context of globalization, its socio-political and cultural aspects. The author highlights the characteristics of Uzbekistan as a multinational society, state policy aimed at maintaining and developing an environment of harmony and tolerance between different ethnic groups. Attention is also paid to global factors affecting interethnic relations, including migration processes, the expansion of the information space and international integration. The article also discusses the legal and regulatory framework, practical measures and future prospects aimed at strengthening national and religious tolerance in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Globalization, Uzbekistan, interethnic relations, tolerance, ethnic groups, social stability, cultural diversity, integration, national policy, migration, international relations, religious tolerance, legal and normative frameworks, social cohesion, intercultural dialogue.

МЕЖНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ОТНОШЕНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ.

Автор: Меликулов Бабур
СамГИИЯ Гуманитарные науки и информация
преподаватель кафедры
информационных технологий.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

Аннотация: В статье анализируется развитие межнациональных отношений в Узбекистане в условиях глобализации, его социально-политические и культурные аспекты. Автор освещает особенности Узбекистана как многонационального общества и политику государства по поддержанию и развитию атмосферы согласия и толерантности между различными этническими группами. Также будет уделено внимание глобальным факторам, влияющим на межэтнические отношения, включая миграционные процессы, расширение информационного пространства, международную интеграцию. В статье также рассматриваются нормативно-правовая база, практические меры и дальнейшие перспективы, направленные на укрепление национальной и религиозной толерантности в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Глобализация, Узбекистан, межнациональные отношения, толерантность, этнические группы, социальная стабильность, культурное разнообразие, интеграция, национальная политика, миграция, международные отношения, религиозная толерантность, правовые и нормативные основы, социальная сплоченность, межкультурный диалог.

Today's world is characterized by rapid changes and processes of mutual integration. Globalization has a significant impact not only on the economic and technological spheres, but also on the socio-political life of society. In particular, interethnic relations are undergoing significant changes under the influence of globalization. As a result of globalization, cultures are becoming closer, and new forms of interethnic dialogue and cooperation are emerging. At the same time, the issues of preserving national identity and traditions, and the development of each nation's own culture remain relevant. Uzbekistan has a rich national and cultural heritage and has historically been formed as a multinational society. Today, representatives of more than 130 nations and ethnic groups live in our country, and they act as a single society, preserving their traditions and cultures. Maintaining interethnic harmony and stability in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of state policy. In our historically and culturally rich country, great attention is paid to strengthening the atmosphere of friendship and solidarity between different nations and peoples. The operation of national cultural centers in our country, the organization of various national holidays and cultural events serve to strengthen interethnic friendship.

In the processes of globalization, issues of awareness of the nation and national identity have risen to the top of the agenda. If globalization is an expression of a transnational reality, then awareness of national and national identity is the initial stage of this reality. It is difficult to understand the universality of globalization without knowing the national reality. If we look at the global reality as a whole, national issues are part of it. Here, the whole and the part, the general and the particular, appear. The socio-philosophical approach requires a harmonious study of them. Globalization is a product of the 20th century, and the awareness of the nation, nationality, and national identity is an even more ancient reality. Even when the nation did not exist, there were views on the nation, ethnos, historical and cultural experiences. It is worth noting that, although there was great interest in the ethnogenesis and ethnic issues of peoples during the Soviet era, there were uncertainties in some theoretical and scientific-methodological issues of ethnology. Especially in the issue of the ethnogenesis of the peoples of Central Asia, the fundamental essence of ethnic terms was not paid attention. For example, the issue of people and nation, the subtle differences between them. The well-known ethnologist, academician K. Shoniyofov, in his works on ethnogenesis and ethnic history, gives good scientific concepts and definitions of ethnos, ethnic unity, tribe, tribal union, elat, people, ethnographic group (subethnos) and ethnic groups, well reveals their content and true essence.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

However, in his works, not enough space is given to the definition of a nation and issues related to its formation. According to K. Shoniyozov, “the terms nation and people have not yet been fully developed in science.” We cannot agree with this opinion. Because the definition of nation and people, the requirements imposed on them, are often similar to each other. However, they do not mean the same concept in essence. Firstly, the people is a social product of feudal society, and the nation is a social product of capitalist society. Secondly, the boundaries of territorial unity from the ethnic factors that organize the people are subject to change due to historical requirements. However, the borders of the nation-state are firm, inviolable, recognized and protected by world public organizations. Thirdly, when a people is formed, it does not always have an ethnic name. Because usually the history of any people is ancient compared to its name. The ancestors of the Uzbeks, who make up the Uzbek ethnos today, were formed as a continuous people in the 11th-12th centuries (see Chapter XIII of this book). Its ethnic name appeared on this land at the beginning of the 16th century. When a people rises to the level of a nation, it must have a name. Fourth, the political association of the people - the state, according to the requirements of history, cannot always be called by the name of the ethnos, but when the people become a nation, the name of its state must also be called by the name of the nation. Fifth, the sense of identity of the ethnos at the level of the people, national pride, devotion to the Motherland, and pride in one's people, according to the rules of the society of that time, are not the same and high in most people. However, when the people rise to the level of the nation, these qualities are at a high level. Sixth, the language of the ethnos does not always receive the status of the state language at the level of the people, when the people rise to the level of the nation, its language certainly receives the status of the state language (in our country, in Uzbekistan, this historical fact happened on October 21, 1989). Seventh, the mentality is formed not at the level of the people of the ethnos, but at the level of the nation, and finally, eighth, when the nation is fully formed, the state is governed by society, that is, the state becomes a mechanism for serving the people, fulfilling the demands and will of the nation in all areas. Thus, the formation of a nation is a long-term historical process, like an ethnogenetic process, and the nation is not a feudal society, but a social product of the capitalist era. The nation is the highest peak of ethnic history, a stage of maturity, the state of the people who have reached this stage is governed by the name of the nation; the state borders governed by the name of the nation are firm, inviolable, recognized by world organizations; within a clear territorial boundary, the language of the nation is elevated to the status of the state language; the level of self-awareness of the population becomes the content of life, the daily lifestyle of citizens; a national mentality characteristic of the nation is formed; the state is governed by society, that is, the state becomes a mechanism for fulfilling the will of the nation. In order for a state to exist, people, peoples, tribes had to unite on some basis - in short, limiting the genesis of a sense of national identity to the formation of a national state is considered illogical and contrary to ethnology. Globalization is prompting us to seek an answer to this fundamental question. Now we are at the stage of expanding the narrow tribe-people-nation system, which requires research on nationality, national identity, and ethnopsychological studies. What are the characteristics of a nation in the era of globalization? S. Otamurodov sees the answer to this question in the definition of a nation. He writes: “A nation is understood as an ethnic unity of people living in a certain territory, having their own state, connected by economic ties, based on a single language, a spirit of national identity, spirituality (in a broad sense), customs, traditions, values, and unity. The researcher emphasizes that there are three scientific innovations in this definition. They are: a) the awareness of national identity is an important sign of a nation; b) the existence of a “nation” as an independent subject, its possession of a certain state; c)

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-3

the fact that a person (people) represents a “nation”. Here, another main difference is expressed in the priority given to spiritual identity, rather than material things, in defining a nation. These features are sufficiently based on and revealed by V. Yakubovsky, K. Shoniyozov, A. Askarov and the literature on ethnology. The novelty that the author is trying to convey, if it can be called scientific, is the study of the problems of globalization in relation to the nation, national-spiritual security. It is inappropriate to associate changes in social existence only with globalization. Historical psychological research is necessary to study the changes taking place in the spirit and life of the nation.

After Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, ensuring interethnic harmony became one of the priority areas of state policy. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees equal rights for representatives of all nationalities. Also, in order to protect the rights and freedoms of representatives of different nationalities A number of laws have been passed. Globalization affects international relations in various ways. On the one hand, due to technological development and migration processes, the cultures of different nations are getting closer to each other. This process serves to strengthen interethnic ties in Uzbekistan. On the other hand, globalization can also lead to the risk of national culture and traditions disappearing. Therefore, various projects are being implemented in Uzbekistan to preserve and develop national values. In particular, special attention is paid to the formation of national and universal values in the education system. The unity and mutual respect of the people of Uzbekistan are an important factor in ensuring interethnic harmony. In ensuring interethnic harmony in Uzbekistan, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5876 of November 15, 2019 “On the Concept of State Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the Field of Interethnic Relations” and the pace of priority areas implemented on the basis of this decree, large-scale democratic reforms, political, economic, social, spiritual liberalization and significant successes achieved in other aspects of public life provide every reason to emphasize that the people of Uzbekistan are united around a single idea - a single goal of achieving noble goals and extremely important tasks in the priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, in the context of ongoing globalization and transformation in international and regional relations, the intensification of economic, political, national, religious and other conflicts in the world, and the growing confrontation in information and cyberspace, a number of urgent issues remain that require their solution in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries, including:

- Further increase in the level of interaction between state bodies and organizations, local executive authorities with civil society institutions in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly relations with foreign countries;
- Establishing a system and mechanisms for monitoring the state of interethnic relations in the field of early prevention and prevention of possible conflict situations and disagreements in society;
- Implementing a complex of educational, information and cultural-educational measures to foster a culture of interethnic communication, study the history and traditions of the people of Uzbekistan;
- improving the work on training, retraining and advanced training of specialists of state bodies, as well as employees of other organizations in the field of further development of interethnic relations and friendly ties with foreign countries. Also, various national holidays, cultural festivals and conferences are organized in Uzbekistan every year, through which interethnic relations are further strengthened. Such events serve to strengthen friendship between peoples.

In order to strengthen interethnic harmony in Uzbekistan, the following strategies are being

implemented:

1. **Improving legislation** - Further development and improvement of laws aimed at ensuring interethnic harmony.
2. **Forming national values in the education system** - Widely promoting national and universal values in schools and higher educational institutions.
3. **Developing cultural events** - Holding events aimed at preserving and developing the cultural heritage of different nations.
4. **Propaganda through the information and media sector** - promoting interethnic friendship through the media and social networks.
5. **Development of international cooperation** - Strengthening cultural exchange and cooperation with other countries.

In the process of globalization, the development of interethnic relations remains an urgent issue in Uzbekistan. The policy pursued by the state serves to strengthen interethnic harmony. Strengthening friendship and cooperation between different nationalities makes a significant contribution to the stability of society, economic development and cultural prosperity. Therefore, effective measures are being taken in Uzbekistan to further develop and strengthen interethnic relations.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE.

1. Шониёзов К. Ўзбек халқининг шаклланиш жараёни, Тошкент-2001, 74-102 бетлар.
2. О'sha asar 77 bet
3. Аҳмадали Асқаров Узбек халқининг этногенези ва этник тарихи (ўқув қўлланма) Тошкент «Университет» 2007-йил 316 bet
4. Imomnazarov M., Eshmuamedova M. – Milliy ma'naviyatimiz asoslari. – Toshkent: Toshkent islom universiteti, 2001. 127-128 bet.
5. Otamuratov S. Globallashuv va milliy-ma'naviy xavfsizlik. –Toshkent.: O'zbekiston NMIU0, 2013.-75b
6. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4597662>